

From Relics to Active Data: An Integrated Meaning-Making Pipeline for Archaeological Archival Collections

Kateryna Lutsai^{#,1}, Pavel Straňák¹, David Novák², and Dana Křivánková^{#,2}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19224825>

Abstract

This paper presents the ATRIUM Meaning-Making Pipeline, an automated workflow that transforms heterogeneous archaeological archives into FAIR-oriented, interoperable datasets. Beyond digitization, we integrate (i) content-specific page classification using the `atrium-page-classification` module, (ii) reading-order recovery and text-line quality classification (distinguishing Clear, Noisy, and Trash lines) via `atrium-alto-postprocess`, (iii) domain-aware translation utilizing `atrium-translator`, and (iv) linguistic enrichment into TEITOK XML via `atrium-nlp-enrich`. By comparing CNNs, Vision Transformers, and hybrid CLIP models, we identify optimal architectures for processing high-volume collections. We also outline the institutional and funding setup that enables processing at scale at ÚFAL, Charles University, supporting a transition from static relics to computationally active data.

Keywords: CAA 2026, ATRIUM, Meaning-Making, FAIR Data, Archaeological Archives, Semantic Enrichment, Reframing Cultural Property, Horizon Europe

¹Institute of Formal and Applied Linguistics, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic, ²Institute of Archaeology of the CAS, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic, [#]Equal contribution

Correspondence

lutsai@ufal.mff.cuni.cz

1. Introduction: Reframing the Archive

As highlighted in the 11th session of CAA 2026, cultural property should not be viewed as a collection of static relics, but as objects that stimulate perception and meaning-making. For archaeological archives, this "reframing" requires a transition from inaccessible physical folders to "active data". Collaboration with EU archaeologists has identified a critical need to systematize large archival collections in Prague (ARUP) and Brno (ARUB), comprising over 1.2 million pages dating back to the 1920s. The challenge lies in the archives' heterogeneity. To move from raw scans to meaningful interpretation, we must overcome multilingual barriers and inconsistent digitization quality. This paper presents an integrated framework developed within the Advancing frontTier Research In the arts and hUMANities (ATRIUM) project, shifting the focus from technical reporting to the creation of a semantic bridge between the past researcher and the modern analyst. ATRIUM addresses this by turning large, traditionally static archaeological collections into computationally active, FAIR-aligned data objects that can be analyzed across infrastructures.

2. The Meaning-Making Pipeline and its Four Modules

The ATRIUM framework is not merely a technical utility but a "Meaning-Making Pipeline". It guides archival material through four stages: (A) Structural Perception, (B) Content Extraction and reading-order recovery, (C) Semantic Harmonization and quality assurance, and (D) Conversational Access via translation and linguistic enrichment. These stages are mapped directly to four modular GitHub repositories Lutsai and Krivankova, 2026.

2.1. Phase A: Structural Perception (`atrium-page-classification`)

Within Phase A, we categorize pages into classes like DRAW, PHOTO, TEXT, and HW, allowing downstream components to select content-specific processing paths. This is managed by the `atrium-page-classification` repository, which relies on fine-tuned Vision Transformers (ViT) and CNNs to automatically sort page scans.

2.2. Phase B & C: Content Extraction and Quality Processing (`atrium-alto-postprocess`)

The `atrium-alto-postprocess` repository bridges structural understanding with semantic content. For Phase B, we normalize document structure by recovering reading order from complex ALTO XML layouts using LayoutReader Xu et al., 2020 and route documents through language-specific processing using fastText. For Phase C, the same repository applies perplexity scoring with DistilGPT2 to categorize text lines into quality tiers: Clear, Noisy, Trash, or Non-text. Degraded *Trash* segments are flagged for targeted recovery rather than standard downstream propagation.

2.3. Phase D.1: Semantic Interoperability (`atrium-translator`)

The pipeline employs a specialized `atrium-translator` module to ensure cross-border accessibility. This phase uses a Tag-and-Protect strategy to preserve technical archaeological terms (e.g., *faience*, *radiocarbon dating*) during translation, leveraging domain vocabularies to bridge the gap between archival traditions.

39 2.4. Phase D.2: Linguistic Enrichment (`atrium-nlp-enrich`)

40 Finally, the `atrium-nlp-enrich` repository applies advanced NLP pipelines, primarily UD-
41 Pipe 2 and NameTag 3 via LINDAT APIs, to extract lemmas, Part-of-Speech tags, and Named
42 Entities. The output is compiled into unified TEITOK XML files, connecting physical layout coor-
43 dinates (bounding boxes) with linguistic metadata for rich, provenance-preserving visualizations.

44 3. System Architecture

45 The overall classification system is implemented as a modular pipeline that transforms raw,
46 disorganized archival documents into a categorized, searchable repository. It is designed to be
47 platform-agnostic, supporting both Unix environments and Windows systems.

48 While the full pipeline involves text post-processing, translation, and enrichment, the core up-
49 stream challenge handled directly on the local cluster is the initial visual sorting. For `atrium-page-classificati`
50 the pipeline applies fine-tuned image classification models—CNNs (e.g., EfficientNetV2 Tan and
51 Le, 2021, RegNetY Radosavovic et al., 2020), Transformers (DiT Li et al., 2022, ViT Dosovitskiy
52 et al., 2020), and hybrid multimodal models (CLIP Radford et al., 2021)—to sort historical page
53 scans.

54 3.1. Interface and Streamlined Input Processing

55 The system bridges the gap between raw scans and model-ready inputs through a robust
56 input layer. For large archives, chunked processing improves memory efficiency by loading and
57 predicting on small batches of images. The architecture consists of a central configuration file
58 (`config.txt`), a command-line entry point (`run.py`), and a lightweight REST API built with FastAPI
59 for interactive testing. Recognizing the sensitivity of archival collections, the architecture is
60 strictly on-premises: processing occurs entirely on local hardware, ensuring restricted data never
61 leaves the institution’s secure network.

62 4. Results: Structural Perception Evaluation

63 We compared CNNs, Transformers, and hybrid CLIP models, fine-tuning and evaluating them
64 on the archival dataset for the Phase A classifier. The test set contains 5,449 images not used in
65 any training subset.

66 4.1. Accuracy and Model Selection

67 Our evaluation demonstrated that CNNs, ViT models, and fine-tuned hybrid CLIP models
68 exceed $\approx 98.5\%$ Top-1 accuracy with parameter budgets below 200M.

- 69 • **RegNetY (CNN):** RegNetY-16GF achieves $\approx 99.16\%$ accuracy with a relatively small pa-
70 rameter count (83.6M) at 224×224 resolution.
- 71 • **EfficientNetV2 (CNN):** EfficientNetV2-M reaches $\approx 98.83\%$ accuracy at 54.1M parame-
72 ters with 384×384 inputs, making it optimal for lower-resource machines.
- 73 • **Transformers (ViT/DiT):** ViT-large reaches $\approx 99.12\%$ Top-1 accuracy but requires sub-
74 stantially more parameters (304.7M) than the best-performing CNNs.
- 75 • **CLIP:** Zero-shot performance is inadequate ($\leq 50\%$). After fine-tuning, all tested CLIP
76 variants exceed $\approx 98.97\%$ accuracy, though they exhibited high inter-model disagree-
77 ment on unlabeled pages compared to image-only models.

Figure 1 – Overview of the ATRIUM meaning-making pipeline and its four main processing modules.

78 Image-only models shared over 90% agreement in their predictions, whereas hybrid models
 79 showed under 65% similarity with any other model. Consequently, image-only models were pre-
 80 ferred for archival sorting. If deployment efficiency is a priority, **RegNetY-16GF** is the strongest
 81 choice: it offers the highest accuracy with a fraction of the parameters of large Transformer
 82 models.

83

5. Conclusion

84 This research addressed the need for automated page-image classification in heterogeneous
 85 historical archives. A reliable page classifier enables content-specific downstream processing
 86 without applying every pipeline to every page. By fine-tuning modern CNNs and Transformer
 87 architectures, we achieved $\approx 97.9\text{--}99.1\%$ classification accuracy.

88 The ATRIUM Meaning-Making Pipeline reframes archaeological archives from static storage
 89 into active, provenance-rich data objects. By sequentially integrating:

- 90 • structural perception (atrium-page-classification),
- 91 • layout-aware extraction and quality classification (atrium-alto-postprocess),
- 92 • and protected translation (atrium-translator)
- 93 • plus linguistic enrichment (atrium-nlp-enrich),

94 we enable interoperable access and lay the groundwork for conversational interfaces grounded
95 in citable archival evidence.

96 Acknowledgements

97 Preprint version 1 of this article has been peer-reviewed and recommended by Peer Commu-
98 nity In Archaeology.

99 Fundings

100 This work was supported by the Advancing frontTier Research In the arts and hUManities
101 (ATRIUM) project (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement 101132163). Compute infrastructure was
102 supported by LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ (MŠMT LM2023062) and OP JAK CZ.02.01.01/00/23_015/0008176.

103 Conflict of interest disclosure

104 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of
105 interest in relation to the content of the article.

106 Data, script, code, and supplementary information availability

107 Software repositories referenced in this paper (atrium-page-classification, atrium-alto-postprocess,
108 atrium-nlp-enrich, and atrium-translator) are publicly available on GitHub ([\[https://github.com/ufal/atrium-project\]](https://github.com/ufal/atrium-project) (<https://github.com/ufal/atrium-project>)). The annotated dataset
109 of labeled pages is available at [\[http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12800/1-5959\]](http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12800/1-5959) (<http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12800/1-5959>) Lutsai and Krivankova, 2026.
110
111

112 References

- 113 Dosovitskiy A, Beyer L, Kolesnikov A, Weissenborn D, Zhai X, Unterthiner T, Dehghani M, Min-
114 derer M, Heigold G, Gelly S, et al. (2020). An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for
115 image recognition at scale. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.11929*.
- 116 Li J, Xu Y, Lv T, Cui L, Zhang C, Wei F (2022). Dit: Self-supervised pre-training for document
117 image transformer. In: *Proceedings of the 30th ACM international conference on multimedia*,
118 pp. 3530–3539.
- 119 Lutsai K, Krivankova D (2026). *Annotated page images from the (archaeological) historical archive*.
120 Version 1.1.0. URL: <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12800/1-6184>.
- 121 Radford A, Kim JW, Hallacy C, Ramesh A, Goh G, Agarwal S, Sastry G, Askell A, Mishkin P, Clark
122 J, et al. (2021). Learning transferable visual models from natural language supervision. In:
123 *International conference on machine learning*. PmLR, pp. 8748–8763.
- 124 Radosavovic I, Kosaraju RP, Girshick R, He K, Dollár P (2020). Designing network design spaces.
125 In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pp. 10428–
126 10436.
- 127 Tan M, Le Q (2021). EfficientNetV2: Smaller Models and Faster Training. In: *International Confer-*
128 *ence on Machine Learning*. PMLR.
- 129 Xu Y, Li M, Cui L, Huang S, Wei F, Zhou M (2020). Layoutlm: Pre-training of text and layout
130 for document image understanding. In: *Proceedings of the 26th ACM SIGKDD international*
131 *conference on knowledge discovery & data mining*, pp. 1192–1200.